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Impact Of Tiv Youths On Community Development

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ABSTRACT

This article examined the impact of Tiv youths on community development. The article traced the core mission of the Tiv Youth Organization (TYO) to the development of Tiv communities. It was anchored on the theory of planned behaviour which emphasized that individuals may intentionally regulate their actions. People are more likely to succeed if they put in more effort to carry out an activity. This review showed that the Tiv youths are expected to develop their communities through agricultural production, preserving culture, fostering peace and social cohesion, contributing to the economy, participating in political activities, infrastructural development, and education activities. However, there were challenges militating against youths' involvement in the community development. These include lack of youth empowerment; limited access to information and training; insufficient youth inclusion in decision-making processes; and systemic issues like corruption and weak governance. To enhance youths' participation in community development, the formation of youth community-based organizations and youth self-help project strategies are recommended.

Keywords: Tiv, Youths, and Community Development

INTRODUCTION

In olden days, Tiv youths were deeply involved in the development of their communities, assisting their parents in farming, particularly growing yams, millet, and sorghum, and engaging in trade. The TIV Youth Organisation (TYO) group was formed with a focus on youth development, community service, and volunteer work in the community. The objectives of Tiv youth organizations are to empower, unite, and advance the Tiv people through youth empowerment, cultural promotion, economic development, political participation, and advocacy for the rights of Tiv people. These goals include enhancing skills, promoting Tiv language and culture, creating economic opportunities, and ensuring the youth's voice is heard in decision-making processes for the benefit of the Tiv nation.

Despite the significant role of Tiv youths in community development, it has been observed that the Tiv youths are not meeting up to their responsibilities in the community development. Most youths migrate to urban areas in search of white-collar jobs, leaving some in their ancestral communities. Today, many of them are engaged in social vices such as stealing, prostitution, political thuggery, cultism, drug abuse, and armed robbery to make quick money. It is against this background that the paper intends to remind the Tiv youths of their impact on community development, the challenges affecting youths' participation in community development, and the strategies for enhancing youths' participation in community development.

Concept Clarification

Youth

Youth refers to the time of life when one is young. The word "youth" can also mean the time between childhood and adulthood, but it can also refer to one's peak, in terms of health, or the period of life known as being a young adult. Youth is described as the period in an individual's life that runs between the end of childhood and entry into the world of work. According to Galstyan (2022), youth has been perceived as a transitional phase of human life. It is someone's period of life during which he/she is a child, before they are a fully matured adult. Tiv youths are young people who belong to the Tiv ethnic group, one of the largest indigenous ethnic groups in Nigeria. Youths are said to possess the following characteristics:

1. Greater physical strength
2. Greater knowledge acquisition propensity
3. Faster rate of learning
4. Faster reaction time
5. Innovative proneness
6. Love for adventure and preference for boldness
7. Minimal risk aversion
8. Less fear of failure
9. Less conservation

Community

A community refers to people living in a place who have face-to-face contact with each other (Goel, 2014). The field theory describes 'social interaction as the most critical feature of community' (Matarrita-Cascante & Brennan in Goel, 2014). Thus, these theories contribute to explaining the community as a structure of relationships whose members are interrelated and function through social interaction. Community relationships could be based on shared identity that is derived from place, ethnicity, culture, interest, or ideology.

Community Development

Community development combines the idea of "community" with "development." Development involves change, improvement, and vitality; a directed attempt to improve participation, flexibility, equity, attitudes, the function of institutions, and the quality of life (Cavaye, 2006). Community development is a process when community members are supported by agencies to identify and take collective actions on issues that are important to them (Chand, 2025). O'Brien, in Mohamud, Muturi and Samantar (2018) viewed community development as referring to the mobilization of community members to actively participate in initiatives aimed at poverty alleviation, solving social problems, and achieving socio-economic development. Community development empowers community members and creates stronger and more connected communities. In the context of this study, community development is a process where youths in a community work together to address shared issues and improve well-being, often with the goal of creating stronger, more resilient, and equitable communities. Key aspects of community development include social, economic, political, cultural, and environmental development.

The process of community development involves identifying community priorities, coordinating group efforts through planning and skill-building, putting plans into action to resolve problems, and monitoring results to aim to bring about long-lasting, constructive change. The process is illustrated in figure 1.

Figure 1: Process of community development (Hasan, 2022)

Theoretical Framework

Theory of Planned Behaviour

The theory assumes that individuals may intentionally regulate their actions. People are more likely to succeed if they put in more effort to carry out an activity. People are more likely to engage in an activity if they have a positive attitude (perception of the behaviour's consequences), a subjective norm (perception of other people's approval), and a high degree of perceived control (perception of the behavior's difficulty). Reducing stigma may benefit from media interventions that aim to improve attitudes and subjective norms and give people a greater sense of power. The theory distinguishes between three types of beliefs that affect an individual's intention to perform a specific behaviour: behavioural beliefs, which translate into attitudes toward the behaviour; normative beliefs, which relate to perceived attitudes of peers and respected figures toward the behaviour; and control beliefs, or perceived ability to perform the behaviour.

The theory relates to this study because it explains how positive attitudes, social norms, and perceived control over participation encourage youth engagement in community initiatives. Engaging youths in the planning, implementation, and evaluation phases of projects ensures their needs are met, and they become future leaders and a stable resource for the community.

Impact of Tiv Youths in Community Development

Tiv youths are expected to impact the community development through following ways:

1. Agricultural productions

Youth engagement in agricultural productions, both consumables (food plant and animal production) and non-consumables (such as rubber and cotton). Areas that can be explored include, but are not limited to: crop productions—maize, rice, beans, wheat, vegetables (green vegetables, tomatoes, peppers, onions, cabbage, cucumbers, carrots, and garden eggs), yams, sweet potatoes, and cassava; tree crop plantations—palm trees, bananas/plantains, cocoa, rubber, coffee; animal productions; fish, poultry, piggery, ranching, and snails.

Young people bring energy, vitality, and innovation into the workforce. Most of the new innovations (both technical and institutional) require a talented agricultural manpower. As an example, promotion of high-value agriculture, precision farming, organic cultivation, hi-tech horticulture, micropropagation, integrated pest disease and nutrient management, floriculture, medicinal and aromatic plant cultivation, high-risk and high-return agricultural ventures like protected agriculture.

Youth's participation in agriculture creates jobs, enhancing food security and nutrition, raising income and economic stability, developing social capital and leadership abilities, and promoting environmental sustainability through community-driven initiatives; agricultural production contributes to the betterment of communities. Geza, Ngidi, Ojo, Adetoro, Slotow, and Mabhaudhi (2021) noted that youth's participation in the agricultural sector contributes to general economic growth.

2. Preserving culture

The youths play a significant role in preserving the culture of the Tiv people through traditions like the Kwagh-hir. Guo and Ward (2022) noted that the involvement of youth in the decision-making processes significantly contributes to rebalancing the power structure and fostering a more democratic and inclusive approach to heritage management systems in the society.

3. Fostering peace and social cohesion

Tiv youth can foster peace and social cohesion by actively participating in peace processes, promoting tolerance through dialogue and education, leading community-based initiatives for reconciliation, and advocating for inclusive policies that address the needs of all young people. According to Saaida (2023), youth involvement in peacebuilding is essential because they contribute new viewpoints, creative ideas, and vitality. Young people are more inclined to be tolerant and receptive to questioning long-standing customs and behaviors that fuel hostilities. Additionally, they can serve as a bridge between various communities and are frequently easier for underprivileged people to access. By involving young people in peacebuilding projects, we can capitalize on their special talents and establish inclusive, participatory processes that produce long-lasting results.

4. Contribution to the economy

The youth are the engine of growth and development (Mimimi & Deebari, 2023). Tiv youth can contribute to the economy by entering the workforce as skilled labour and consumers, creating jobs and wealth through entrepreneurship, and driving innovation through new technologies and ideas.

5. Participation in political activities

The youths can get involved in political activities by participating in civic education and advocacy, joining or starting youth-led organizations, taking part in formal political procedures like voting and running for office, and using media and technology to spread their message and inspire others. These are all ways that young people can get involved in politics. Iringe-koko and Adedunmola (2024) asserted that youth are increasingly involved in political activities, including voting, participating in political parties and organisations, and engaging in activism.

6. Infrastructural development

The youths are deeply concerned with the process of creating, improving, and maintaining the fundamental physical and organizational structures necessary for a society or economy to function and grow. Adesiji, Omotesho, Komolafe, Oni, and Adereti (2014) found that youth participate in the building of schools, construction of health centers, building of town halls, road construction, building of post offices, and market construction.

7. Education activities

The youths' participation in educational development. Abdullahi (2014) postulates that youth are the backbone of any national development. They play a very paramount role in educational development by offering vitality, creative thinking, and a distinct digital viewpoint, all of which can result in more appropriate and successful educational initiatives.

Challenges Militating against Youth Involvement in Community Development

The challenges militating against youth involvement in the community development include the following:

1. Lack youth empowerment

Most of the youths in our communities are not employed or empowered. As such, they do not have the resources to use as their contribution to community development. Abamara (2014) submitted that the majority of youths in Nigeria cannot provide daily meals for themselves and their family, let alone start a family of their own. What causes this persistent poverty among young people? In actuality, Nigeria's labor market is oversaturated and overworked, and the country is currently facing a high unemployment rate. Only around 10% of the more than 9,000 graduates who leave our postsecondary schools each year will find gainful employment following their National Youth Service Corps program, according to data.

2. Limited access to information and training

Limited access to information and training creates a knowledge gap, limiting skill acquisition and hindering awareness of available opportunities. Mohamud, Muturi, and Samantar (2018) access of youths to information and training allows them to share the skills and knowledge that they need.

3. Insufficient youth inclusion in decision-making processes

Insufficient inclusion of youths in decision-making possess a sense of powerlessness, reducing the perceived value of their contributions, creating a lack of relevant opportunities, and limiting the development of their leadership skills. Ali (2014) asserted that Youth employ a variety of strategies, including advocacy, social action, popular education, and mass mobilization. Youth participation in direct decision-making or advisory roles in making public policy decisions impact on social change.

4. Systemic issues like corruption and weak governance

Corruption and poor governance impede community development, undermining public confidence, impeding economic progress, warping the rule of law, and impeding the successful execution of development initiatives. The youths are vulnerable to multiple forms of corruption that result in severe negative impacts spanning the social, economic development of their lives and the community (Bergin, 2024). Other challenges include lack of basic equipment; fraud, dishonesty, and corruption among leaders; politics; rivalries and envy among youths; and inability to accept change in traditional and cultural practices and technology.

Strategies for enhancing Youths Participation in Community Development

1. Formation of youth community based organisations

Youth community-based organisations enhance community development. Aminu (2012) opined that the community-based organizations enhance community development through:

- a. Development, promotion and implementation of development projects sustainable for the benefit of their communities
- b. Mobilising members of the community for national development
- c. Strengthening community resources management
- d. Improving the general skills of youths to be productive
- e. Promoting a sustainable human development
- f. Encouraging the participation of the marginalised communities in the promotion of rural development that affects them. - To ensure proper accountability of the community resources.

2. Youths and Self-Help Projects in Nigeria

The youths have a solution for themselves and their communities. Aminu (2012) stressed that the youths can mobilize their fellow youths to embark on community development and self-help projects. The self-help projects contribute to community development in the following ways:

- a. Education of the rural community members on the use of improved farming techniques
- b. Clearing and draining of drainages and culverts in the community
- c. Provision of water through sinking of boreholes of ordinary dug-out wells
- d. Renovation of clinics and other health facilities in the rural communities
- e. Construction of access roads in the rural communities

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2. Youths and Self-Help Projects in Nigeria

- f. privileged in the community by provision of useful materials
- g. Sensitization of the rural dwellers on health-related and security issues

CONCLUSION

Tiv youths are educated, innovative, and technologically inclined and they are the engine power of all Tiv communities. Based on the characteristics possessed by these category of people, the youths are expected to play significant roles in the community development. However, it is regrettable that the youths of today cause more harm to their communities than good. In many situations, the youths are not completely blamed for becoming a nuisance in their communities. The government is also held responsible for unacceptable behaviour of the youths. Nevertheless, the members of the Tiv Youths Organization (TYO) could reconsider their cultural norms and values that are requisite for community development in Tiv land.

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